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Basic Digital Skills: Next Critical Skills Set towards a Resilient Nation

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Abstract

The world is evolving fast in terms of digital technological advancements. Nevertheless, most Malawians still lack basic digital skills. This paper starts by defining basic digital skill, learning from different frameworks through strategic document review, then justifies why basic digital skills should be introduced early in basic education institutions and be considered on the same scale of importance as traditional literacy skills. The paper then advocates for early uptake and acceptance of basic digital skills as mandatory life skills in Malawi's basic education system and that the basic digital skills should be treated in the same level of necessity as traditional literacy skills. The paper further accentuates that the spectrum of digital skills has grown tremendously in recent years such that attaining competitively productive Information and Communication Technology (ICT) graduates requires the introduction of entry-level digital skills to be consigned further down on the Malawi national qualification framework to primary schools, adult literacy institutions and out-of-school training houses. This would, not only leave the masses of learners who drop from the education system with necessary basic digital skills to access digital information for their livelihood and lifelong learning, but also create opportunity for undergraduate university students to meaningfully engage emerging technologies. Lastly, the paper alludes that such restructuring of content would accord ICT graduates with modern skills that, not only matches the current and projected market demand of digital skills, but also adequately prepare the graduates to follow the cutting-edge of the fast-advancing digital skills continuum. This would entrench the necessary ICT-enabled resilience of Malawi as a nation.

Keywords: digital skills, qualification framework, emerging technologies, 4th industrial revolution

1 Introduction

All economies of the world experience the impact of and some are catalyzed by digital technologies. The benefits expected and accrued from these technologies, collectively referred to as digital dividends, have potential of strengthening the resilience of these economies. Digital technologies boost growth, expand opportunities and improve service delivery thereby adding value to gross output in the economies (WDR, 2016).

Digital technologies are restructuring the market place changing the patterns of production and consumption. Digital technology is becoming increasingly intertwined with everyday life: from schooling and education to political engagement and even financial and health management (Grand-Clement, 2017). Estimates for 2019 indicated that 4.1 billion people were using internet. Data flow had grown from 100GB per day in 1992 to 46600 GB per second in 2017. It is projected to grow further to 150, 700 GB per second by 2022 (WITSA, 2019). Due to the rapid growth of digital technologies, it is becoming increasingly difficult to live in contemporary society without using digital technologies as more and more day-to-day routine activities can be done with the support of digital technologies. Further, the implication of the big data and the increasing adoption of emerging technologies is that the world economy is transforming at a

rapid pace (WITSA, 2019). It follows, therefore, that those not able to access these technologies are at risk of being excluded from socio-economic provisions and opportunities in society (Devaux et al., 2017).

The aggregated impact of the digital technologies, however, is not evenly distributed. For digital technologies to benefit everyone and everywhere, it is required that we close in on the remaining digital divide, especially in internet access. Even then, greater digital adoption on its own would not be enough. To get the most out of the digital revolution, countries will need to work on the “analog complements” by strengthening regulations that ensure competition among businesses, adapting workers’ skills to the demands of the new economy, and ensuring that institutions are accountable (WDR, 2016).

The legal and regulatory framework is the most critical aspect with respect to the activities associated with digital economy. The overall impact of the digital economy will be felt across all sectors if the (big) digital data is managed and analyzed efficiently (WBG, 2019). This can only be possible with leveraging of the emerging technologies such as Data science, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Deep learning, Internet of things, Blockchain and 5G network technologies. Furthermore, connectivity within the country and across countries is of prerequisite importance.

While nations are building the foundations of the digital economy, there is need to adopt a comprehensive ecosystem approach. The digital transformation must aim at digitally enabling every individual, business and government by 2030 (WDR, 2016). Demand-driven approach is necessary in defining the requisite elements of the digital economy. More importantly, the skills required in the digital economy need to be mapped against the existing supply of skills in labour force. Any existing gaps in digital skills should be addressed by appropriately aligning the skill development initiatives to the demands.

2 Economic and Digital Landscape of Malawi

Malawi is considered as a least developed country (LDC) by global classifications (WBG, 2019). The gross national income (GNI) per capita for Malawi is at US\$380 and is less than the global average of US\$11,599 (WBG, 2019). Malawi also scores low on the human assets index (HAI) at 52.5 which is less than both the average for LDCs at 53.1 and the average of developing countries at 76.4 (UN, 2018). The economic vulnerability index of Malawi at 47.1 is higher than the averages of both LDCs at 41.3 and developing countries at 34.7. These and more related indicators suggest that the economic landscape of Malawi is not really favourable for accruing meaningful dividends of a digital economy, unless Malawi strategically capitalizes on its bulging young population.

On network readiness index (NRI) Malawi is ranked 117th out of 121 (WITSA, 2019). NRI is one of the leading global indices on application and impact of ICT in economies around the world. The ICT sector forms an essential part of the digital infrastructure requirement to ensure availability of telecom, broadband, computers and software across the country that feed a digital economy. Malawi has one of the weakest connectivity infrastructures in the Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) region (SARUA, 2008). In order to counter digital divide and provide users with universal network coverage, Malawi needs to build an efficient digital infrastructure. This should immediately be followed by putting in place mechanisms for affordable access to internet.

Digital technology innovation ecosystem of Malawi is not only underdeveloped, but also highly fragmented. For a digital ecosystem to have impact, it needs to have a strong integration with different

actors of the economy. Nevertheless, there is significant contribution to the economy from the informal sectors (WBG, 2019). To adequately prepare the youth employed in informal sectors and those pursuing entrepreneurship, effective mapping of skills demands and corresponding training programs is critical. Incorporating digital literacy as an integral part of basic education curricula would allow for skill up-gradation to competitive national and global levels. We therefore advocate for early uptake and acceptance of basic digital skills as mandatory life skills in our (Malawi's) basic education system and that the basic digital skills should be treated in the same level of necessity as reading, writing, and numeracy. We believe that, apart from digital infrastructure and access to internet, the greatest challenge to reaping meaningful digital dividends lies in building relevant skills for a digital economy. For a digital economy to thrive, digital skills must also function together with other abilities such as strong literacy and numeracy skills, critical and innovative thinking, complex problem solving, an ability to collaborate, and socio-emotional skills in the connected economy and society.

3 (Basic) Digital skills

Before we proceed further, it is important to develop a common understanding of (basic) digital skills. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines digital skills as a range of the abilities to use digital devices, communication applications and network to access and manage information (UNESCO, 2018). *The entry-level (basic) digital skills to this range of skills are the basic functional skills required to use digital devices and online applications. They are considered as critical component of the new set of literacy skills in the digital era, in the same level as the traditional skills such as reading, writing and numeracy.*

The United Kingdom Digital Skills Taskforce (UKDST, 2014), single out *basic digital skills as skills needed to interact with digital technologies, and emphasizes that such skills are necessary life skills.*

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2016), goes further than just defining digital skills. It categorizes the digital skills into: a) ICT specialists skills which are competencies to develop, operate and maintain ICT systems; b) Advanced users skills which are described as a set of skills for 'competent users of advanced, and often sector-specific, software tools'; and c) *Basic users skills which are for a group of users described as 'competent users of generic tools (e.g. office suites and internet-related tools such as browser and email clients) needed for the information society, e-government and working life'. ICTs for this user group are mainly used as a communicating tool.*

In Development Economics 'The Future Digital Skills Needs of the UK Economy' Report, (FDSN, 2013) digital skills are defined as 'the attributes that allow individuals and businesses both to use digital equipment and to access, create or share digital information via the internet and thereby benefit from opportunities in the modern economy'. The report sets out what it calls 'a functional hierarchy of these digital skills' as follows: a) Advanced digital skills which are skills linked to 'the creation and/or strategic exploitation of new digital applications, including more advanced programming and coding involved in the creation of new software'. Such skills also cover 'the strategic business skills needed to convert ideas into successful commercial projects and ventures'; b) Intermediate-level digital skills which are skills needed to implement and manage on a day-to-day basis the applications developed by those with advanced skills, but they may also provide contributions to the development of digital content, provision of system support and maintenance; and c) *Entry-level (basic) digital skills which are skills related to 'the use of digital*

applications designed, developed and promoted by other, involving for example searching for and/or the capturing and recording of digital data across a wide variety of business and public services, the administration of databases, the monitoring of data, contributing to the management of digital content’.

In defining digital skills for the UK economy, the Department of Business Innovation and Skills and the Department of Culture Media and Sports of United Kingdom (DBIS&DCMSUK, 2016) broadly categorize digital skills into: a) *Basic digital literacy skills (for empowering individuals) which are skills needed by every citizen to become ‘digitally literate’.* These are the skills needed to carry out basic functions such as using digital applications to communicate and carry out basic internet searches; b) Digital skills for the general workforce (up-skilling for the digital economy) which include all skills belonging to Category a) plus skills needed in a workplace and generally linked to the use of applications developed by ICT specialists. While the digital skills needed by the workforce are likely to differ across sectors, there will be some minimum requirements linked to processing information that will be applicable across all sectors; c) Digital skills for ICT professions (digitally innovative and creative individuals, organizations and businesses) which include Categories a) and b), plus skills needed to work across the diverse ICT sector. They include digital skills linked to the development of new digital technologies, and new products and services. Such skills are needed if a nation is to compare favourably with other nations in relation to ICT investment and utilization.

Based on the strategic literature review of the various frameworks above, we affirm that much as digital skills form a continuum, *basic digital skills are fundamental entry-level functional skills required to make rudimentary use of digital devices and applications.* These skills can be seen as literacy life skills that are essential for being able to access and use digital devices/technologies and access digital information. These skills allow an individual to operate devices, to connect to the internet, to set up accounts and profiles, and to access information and resources. Basic skills are essential life skills in the same lenses as traditional literacy skills such as reading, writing and numeracy. It is therefore only proper that all such skills are appropriately placed on the qualification framework, to the basic education part of the education systems hierarchy. In our subsequent articles, we intend to develop a detailed matrix of the recommended basic digital skills, contextualized to Malawi’s digital ecosystem. We will also discuss investment projections if Malawi nation were to opt for our proposition.

4 Rationale for placing basic digital skills training in the basic education sector

The (Malawi) National Education Sector Plan (NESP 2008 – 2017), gives both national and global definitions of basic education. The understanding at national level and within the Ministry of Education (MoE) is that basic education implies only primary education. However, NESP is quick to acknowledge that, globally, basic education is for the age range starting from 0 – 16 years old and it includes pre-school (Early Childhood Development), Primary education, adult literacy as well as out-of-school youth. Pre-School is for 5 years old and below. Primary education is for 6 – 13 years old and it has eight standards. Out-of-school youth education and adult literacy is for those aged 15 years and above; however, in practice out-of-school youth include children who could be under primary school but are not attaining primary education. In this paper, we opt for the global definition of basic education, particularly because it includes two important non-formal groups of the population, namely the adult literacy group and the out-of-school youth group. The two groups cover a large proportion of the Malawi’s population.

We argue that mainstreaming basic digital skills training to the broader basic education sector as is defined in the global view, will widen the reach and enhance the impact of such training. For example, adult illiteracy in Malawi remains high, particularly among women and the poor. According to the 2005 Integrated Household Survey, only 64% of adults (15 years and above) were literate. The corresponding literacy rates for male adults and female adults were 76% and 52%, respectively. The link between literacy, development and poverty reduction is that literate people are able to access information pertaining to their development needs from a variety of sources. Literate people understand and easily follow instructions for performing various development activities. Including this non-formal group of people in the entrenchment of digital literacy will be critical for inclusive participation of citizenry in the digital economy.

In addition, the provision of non-formal basic education to out-of-school youth is relatively new in Malawi. In recent past, the provision was in partnership with the then Ministry of Youth Development and Sports and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). The then Ministry of Education, Science and Technology was piloting the implementation of Complementary Basic Education (CBE) in four districts. Nevertheless, out-of-school youth education is essential as it aims at providing essential knowledge, skills and values to promote self-reliance, encourage lifelong learning and full participation in societal development, (NESP, 2008 – 2017). Out-of-school youth programmes target those who dropped out of primary school and those who have never attended school. Including these youths in the digital literacy initiative will be important for their participation in the digital economy.

Overall, the longest existing structure under basic education and within the entire education sector is primary education. Primary education is the sub-sector which affects the greatest number of people, and which is the basis for all other formal education sectors. Good primary education is valuable both for those who leave school at the end of primary, and for those who continue with their education. Only if the primary sector functions well can students gain the basic knowledge to progress to secondary and higher education institutions. World-wide, research shows that people who have good primary education are likely to be more productive in life than those who do not have, (WDR, 2016). Injecting basic digital skills at this level will be very strategic not only in freeing the higher levels of the education hierarchy to advance digital training, but also netting in a larger population of the youths who drop out on the way. For example, Education Sector Implementation Plan II (ESIP II, 2014 – 2018), reveals that only 47% of primary pupils from 2007 Standard 1 Cohort progressed to standard 6 within expected years. This is because each year between 3-15% of pupils drop out, depending on the standard, while between 14-15% failed to progress to the next standard and had to repeat the year. Standard 8 survival rate was 35% for girls and 41% for boys. An average survival rate of 38% thus suggests that an estimated 62% of Standard 1 entrants would not survive the primary school cycle within 8 years.

The situation becomes even more worrisome in post-primary levels. Access to public secondary schools is very restrictive as it is based on selection with a transition from primary to secondary education of just 32%. The tertiary gross enrolment rate is 0.4% – among the lowest in Africa. At 45 female students per 100,000 inhabitants, the rate is much lower than that for males which averages 86 students per 100,000 inhabitants (ESPII, 2014 – 2018).

Therefore, placing basic digital skills development in basic education system, would not only adequately equip our graduates with cutting-edge competitive skills, but also leave those who drop out on the way with necessary skills for lifelong learning and meaningfully competing for employment and entrepreneurial

opportunities. The (intellectual) demand accorded to acquiring of these basic skills scales comparably with that of contemporary traditional literacy skills that are already being offered in the basic education sector. The nation will only need to strategically invest in order to create conducive environment for the development of such critical life skills.

5 Conclusion

We have campaigned for early uptake and acceptance of basic digital skills as mandatory life skills in Malawi's basic education system and that such skills should be treated in the same level of necessity as reading, writing, and numeracy. Firstly, the pyramid structure of the Malawi education systems implies that the lower the level in the structure at which the training is introduced, the larger the proportion of the beneficiaries of the training. Secondly, we have accentuated that the fast growth of the spectrum of digital skills implies that if we were to have competitively productive ICT graduates, then basic digital skills needed to be consigned further down on to basic education institutions. This would create enough room for an undergraduate university student to meaningfully engage emerging technologies such as (Big) Data Science, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Deep learning, Block chain, 5G Networks, which define the 4th industrial revolution. Such restructuring of content would accord our ICT graduates with modern skills that not only would match the current and projected market demand of digital skills, but also adequately prepare the graduates to follow the front of the fast-advancing digital skills continuum. This would entrench the necessary ICT-enabled resilience of Malawi as a nation. In our subsequent articles, we will develop a detailed matrix of the recommended basic digital skills, contextualized to Malawi's digital ecosystem. We will also discuss investment projections if Malawi nation were to opt for our proposition.

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